

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER/EPOXY FILAMENT WOUND LAMINATES EXPOSED TO HYGROTHERMAL CONDITIONING

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to evaluate the effect of hygrothermal conditioning on the tensile, in-plane shear and viscoelastic properties of carbon fiber/epoxy laminates (fiber volume fraction $\approx 70\%$). The flat unidirectional laminates were manufactured by filament winding process using a KUKA robot and the composites were cured under hot compression molding. The laminates were later exposed to hygrothermal conditioning. All composite samples were tested before and after environmental conditioning in a hygrothermal chamber. Elastic and strength tensile properties reduced for aged specimens, e.g. [0]₄ sample presented a reduction of 18% in tensile strength and 8% in elastic modulus. Shear strength and modulus followed the same trend, and shear modulus reduced in about 38%. Tensile and shear post-test specimens presented accepted failure modes, since for instance, shear specimens failed at the gage section with delaminations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites are commonly used in applications with high structural demand, such as marine, aeronautic and aerospace sectors. They are widely employed mainly due to advantages such as corrosion resistance, high specific properties and good damage tolerance. Advanced composites are continuously replacing metallic parts in several fields, justifying the need for a reliable database for design.

Among the manufacturing processes available for advanced polymer composites, filament winding (FW) stands out being able to produce from flat laminates to elbows and curved-surface structures. The high fiber volumetric fraction, precision in angle deposition, tensioned reinforcement and continuous fibers are the main features of FW. The Oil & Gas sector, in particular, is increasingly replacing metallic-based by composite structures based on the need to increase payload in marine structures by reducing weight and the lack of corrosion of these materials. Indeed, pipelines, subsea systems and submersible structures are constantly operating under aggressive environments, which reduce and change the mechanical response of the composite, making them less tolerant to damage and sometimes leading to premature failure.

Prediction of failure and damage in composites is typically complex due to their orthotropic characteristic, and it becomes even more complicated when the material is under extreme weathering. When exposed to these environments, they can absorb moisture, which affects the long-term durability and properties of the composite [1]. Since high-performance carbon fibers absorb virtually no moisture compared to the matrix, absorption is largely matrix-dominated [2], suggesting that matrix-dominated failure mechanisms will be greatly affected. In addition, moisture absorption degrades fiber-matrix bonding, reducing microstructural integrity.

Moisture permeation is dominated by diffusion, capillarity and/or transport by micro-cracks, and the rate of moisture uptake varies with the type of matrix, fiber orientation, water temperature and humidity

[3]. Moisture wicking promotes changes in mechanical, thermo-mechanical and thermo-physical behavior of the matrix by plasticization, swelling and hydrolysis [1,4].

Moisture absorption when allied to high temperatures may induce irreversible structural changes in the polymeric network, such as cracking, fiber-matrix debonding and chemical degradation. The composite damage may change the weight uptake, since cracking and blistering cause higher uptake, whereas the leaching of small molecule components results in a gradual decrease in weight gain [5].

Ultraviolet radiation (UV) can also degrade the matrix and cause irreversible structural changes. UV radiation can cause photolytic, photo-oxidative and thermo-oxidative reactions in the matrix, and the degradation can range from a simple discoloration to a substantial loss of mechanical properties [6]. UV photons can impose C–C chain scission of the chemical bonds of the matrix, leading to photo-oxidation [7]. Another effect is the cross-linking, which restricts molecular mobility and reduces the ability of the material to accommodate externally applied deformation [8].

Marine structures sometimes operate under combined UV and seawater influence being both agents detrimental to polymeric composites. Botelho et al. [9] studied the effect of moisture, UV, salinity and temperature on the thermal properties of PEI/glass fiber composites, and UV showed the greatest harm to the thermal and viscoelastic properties of the laminates. Also, Botelho et al. [10] evaluated the effect of different hygrothermal conditioning on the in-plane shear behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy composites and Mouzakis et al. [7] studied accelerated environmental ageing of glass/polyester composites focusing on their dynamic mechanical and thermal properties.

On this context, this paper deals with the effect of the environmental conditioning (accelerated water immersion) on the tensile, in-plane shear and viscoelastic properties of filament-wound flat carbon fiber/epoxy laminates.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials & manufacturing

The raw materials used in this work were:

- Carbon fiber/epoxy towpregs from TCR Composites, where the carbon fiber is Toray T700-12K-50C and the epoxy resin system is UF3369;
- Rectangular stainless steel mandrel, with 327 mm × 228 mm;
- Release agent WB 2700, from AXEL Plastics.

The flat laminates were manufactured (Figure 1) using a KUKA robot KR 140 L100 with control and peripheral devices from MFTech. The delivery eye is able to process up to four towpregs simultaneously. The design and manufacturing of the laminates were aided by CADWind2007, which is a CAD and CAM software for filament winding. The unidirectional composites with constant fiber volume fraction of ≈70% (measured according to ASTM D3171-11) were cured by hot compression molding under 3 ton, for 150 min for 150 min at 125 °C.

2.2 Weathering

Accelerated water immersion: The carbon fiber/epoxy specimens were exposed to a combination of temperature and humidity for 60 days at 110 °C under a relative humidity of 90% in a climatic chamber.

The hygrothermal exposure was carried out following the recommendations of ASTM D5229M-14 standard. Firstly, sample goes through a drying cycle following these steps: i) weight the sample; (ii) place it in an oven at 110 °C for 24 h; iii) remove the sample from the oven, put in a desiccator and later weight it; iii) return it to the oven for 3 h under 110 °C. These steps are repeated until the specimen reaches the mass equilibrium, and only then they are placed in the hygrothermal chamber for 60 days at 80 °C and 90% humidity. The sample mass was periodically monitored to evaluate moisture absorbing by using Equation (1).

$$M = \left| \frac{M_w - M_d}{M_d} \right| \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where M , is the mass gain percentage, M_w and M_d are wet and dry masses, respectively.

Figure 1: Manufacturing of a flat unidirectional laminate by filament winding.

2.3 Characterization

The unidirectional composites were cut longitudinally and transversely to the fiber direction. All mechanical testing were carried out using an Instron 3382 universal testing machine with 100 kN and 5 kN load cells.

- **Tensile:** This test was performed at a constant speed (2 mm/min) in five tabbed coupons of controlled geometry dimensions following ASTM D3039-14. From this test, the elastic moduli, tensile strengths and Poisson's ratio were obtained. The specimens were tested with two analogical extensometers, one longitudinal and another transversal, which were removed just prior to rupture.
- **In-plane shear:** The test chosen to obtain shear properties was the V-notched rail shear method (ASTM D7078-12), which is recommended for high-modulus unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite materials. The specimen (dimensions: 76 mm × 56 mm × 2.8 mm) was centrally V-notched on both sides. The notch angle is 90° and the radius is 1.3 mm. Cross-head speed was 1.5 mm/min and the shear modulus was determined on 6 samples by using a strain gage rosette aligned at ±45° at the mid-section of the sample (as seen in Figure 2). Shear modulus was calculated within the 1500 – 4000 $\mu\epsilon$ range and the engineering shear strain (γ_{12}) was calculated using Eq. (2).

$$\gamma_{12} = |\epsilon_{+45}| + |\epsilon_{-45}| \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: V-notched shear test with a bonded rosette.

- **Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA):** DMA was used to evaluate the influence of weathering on the viscoelastic behavior and the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polymeric composite. Analysis was carried out under single-cantilever bending mode using 20 mm × 10 mm × 2.8 mm specimens at 1 Hz frequency and for a maximum displacement of 10 mm. Temperature was varied from 25 to 250 °C with a heating rate of 3 °C/min, using a TA Instruments 2980 DMA Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Moisture uptake

Figure 3 presents the mass uptake for the 0° unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy tensile coupons (average of 5 coupons) submitted to hygrothermal conditioning at 80 °C and 90% of relative humidity. The reproducibility of the uptake data is fairly good among different specimens and the fitting curve ratifies the obtained data with being effective in represents the water absorption of the material. The uptake curve complied with Fick's law, with the mass gain initially increasing linearly with respect to time^{1/2} and gradually leveling off. The initial stage till pseudo-equilibrium is typical of a thermally activated Fickian response, whereas at longer times the uptake occurs at a lower rate due to a combination of mechanisms such as relaxation of the glassy epoxy network, filling of micro-voids and debonded zones with water by wicking [11]. Thus, moisture absorption is expected to take place via diffusion, in which water molecules are transported from higher concentration areas to lower moisture concentration areas.

Figure 3: Mass gain of the specimens and the fitting curve.

Water saturation ($\approx 0.37\%$) was reached in around 33 days, and the maximum mass uptake is about 0.41%, is found after 42 days of conditioning, being typical of epoxy resins. Moreover, the mass uptake profile is lower compared to literature data for the same matrix and fiber herein used [4,10,11], what can be justified by the high fiber volumetric fraction and a good compaction of the layers.

3.1 Viscoelastic properties

Figure 4 shows the storage modulus (E') for the two families of composites studied, unconditioned and after hygrothermal conditioning. As expected, storage modulus for 0° specimens is higher than the 90° ones in all states (glassy, elastomeric and rubbery). This particular DMA analysis was performed under bending mode, which is markedly dependent on fiber orientation, being stiffer for longitudinal fibers along the length of the specimen. Analyzing the conditioning effect, it is clear that unconditioned specimens have higher storage modulus than the weathered ones, being this behavior related to the plasticizing effect promoted by moisture absorption.

The aged composites have similar behavior at the glassy state, once this phenomenon may occurs due to a post-curing that may take place during ageing. The relatively high temperatures involved, although not severe enough to break chemical bonds of the polymer [7], may contributed to the appearance of free radicals in the epoxy molecules, leading to further cross-linking [8].

Figure 4: Storage modulus of the unconditioned and weathered specimens.

The loss modulus (E'') is related to energy dissipation in the material under combined mechanical and temperature loadings. Composite materials with poor interfacial bonding and fiber/matrix adhesion are prone to dissipate more energy. Figure 5 displays a decrease in E'' after hygrothermal weathering. Also, E'' is also higher when fibers are oriented longitudinally to the loading direction because the specimen with longer fiber loses less energy to support the flexural loading.

Some specimens presented a more flattened loss peak, as can be seen in Figure 5. Analyses of the curves show that the behavior was more affected by fiber orientation than the weathering, and the specimens with fibers at 0° presented much higher peaks. For the 90° specimens, the aged laminate dissipated slightly less energy. This can be attributed to the inhibition of the relaxation processes in the composites, decreasing mobility at the fiber/matrix interface and a higher number of chain segments upon water absorption.

Figure 5: Loss modulus of the unconditioned and weathered composites.

The E''/E' ratio defines $\tan \delta$, formerly known as damping factor. Damping properties give the balance between viscous and elastic phases in a polymer network system. In composites, damping is influenced by content, type and fiber orientation, viscoelastic nature of the matrix and/or fiber, matrix/fiber interface as well as fiber/matrix interactions and void content [12]. Damping is also caused by dissipation of energy at matrix cracks, which is accentuated in hygrothermally aged specimens.

$\tan \delta$ curves are shown in Figure 6. Both unconditioned specimens showed similar temperature at the peak (i.e. T_g , the glass transition temperature), and both conditioned samples showed similar and lower T_g values. The weathering effect on the composites is more clearly observed in this figure, i.e. the conditioned specimens show larger areas under the peak and lower T_g , suggesting matrix degradation.

Figure 6: Tan delta of the unconditioned and weathered specimens.

Table 1 presents the T_g extracted from: (i) intersection from the extension of the elastomeric plateau and glass state of the storage modulus curves, (ii) the loss modulus peak, and (iii) the $\tan \delta$ peak. The unconditioned 0° specimen shows the highest T_g , but the aged aged_[0]₄ specimen shows the smallest value for all methods, where this specimen is more damaged by the aging, pointing that fiber orientation has no direct effect on the viscoelastic characteristics of the polymer.

<i>Specimen</i>	<i>T_g (°C) from onset E' drop</i>	<i>T_g (°C) from E'' peak</i>	<i>T_g (°C) from $\tan \delta$ peak</i>
<i>aged_[0]₄</i>	78.3	91.0	98.1
<i>non-aged_[0]₄</i>	35.2	47.7	57.9
<i>aged_[90]₄</i>	68.9	84.8	94.7
<i>non-aged_[90]₄</i>	44.7	57.8	67.4

 Table 1: T_g determined by different methods.

3.1 Mechanical properties

Figure 7 presents the load \times displacement curves for non-aged and aged 0° coupons. Conditioning reduced the tensile strength of the laminates, from 1409 ± 131 MPa to 1191 ± 114 MPa, around 18%. The tensile behavior of the coupons must be highlighted, once the non-aged specimens present more than one peak load, due to continuous breaking of the filaments, once after starting to fail in some filaments, the specimen keep supporting a portion of the load, presenting a “quasi-brittle” behavior, which is typical for filament wound composites due to the high number of long filaments oriented in loading direction. The same behavior was not observed for aged composites, which presented a fully brittle behavior, as shows Figure 7(b). This behavior is attributed to the matrix plasticization, which degrades the fiber/matrix interface.

Figure 8a-b shows tensile behavior of the 90° oriented composites. A brittle behavior is dominant for both non-aged and aged specimens and the ultimate load is significantly lower compared to longitudinally oriented laminates.

Even though the load \times displacement curves somewhat differ for the various longitudinally oriented specimens, all coupons showed similar failure mode (see Figure 9a), with a sudden failure of the filaments. All 10 fractures (5 for aged and 5 non-aged) were characterized as explosive gage middle (XGM). The failure mode for all 90° samples was also similar, for conditioned and non-conditioned coupons, presenting a lateral gage middle (LGM) failure (see Figure 9a), with only one lateral at the top tab (LAT) failure.

Figure 7: Load × displacement tensile curves for non-aged (a) and aged (b) for 0° specimens.

Figure 8: Load × displacement tensile curves for non-aged (a) and aged (b) for 90° specimens.

Figure 9: Typical failure modes for non-aged $[0]_4$ (a) and non-aged $[90]_4$ (b) tensile specimens.

Stress vs strain (obtained with extensometers) data for the tensile testing of the aged specimens are shown in Figure 10 (the respective curves for non-aged specimens were published in a previous work [13]). The final properties may be summarized as: (i) Non-aged: $E_{1,t} = 129.8 \pm 5.6$ GPa and $E_{2,t} = 9.1 \pm 0.5$ GPa, and ii) Aged: $E_{1,t} = 119.7 \pm 4.1$ GPa and $E_{2,t} = 6.3 \pm 0.8$ GPa. A more significant drop in elastic properties for E_2 may be justified considering that this property is more influenced by the characteristics of the matrix, which is the most damaged constituent of the composite under hygrothermal ageing.

Figure 10: Stress × strain behavior for aged 0° (a) and 90° (b) specimens.

Figure 11 displays the shear stress × time curves for the specimens submitted to shear test through V-notched rail test method. These curves (Figure 11) shows typical behavior of shear, where after 50 s most of specimens started to delaminate. A good compaction of the laminates manufactured by filament winding allied to a great method to evaluate the shear behavior of composite laminates can be noticed in these graphs, since all coupons failed by delamination and horizontal micro-cracks at the gage area.

Shear tests may be used to assess the fiber/matrix interface and the matrix itself, since this is also a matrix-dominated property. The breaking load was in average c.a. 40% lower for conditioned specimens, indicating a strong ageing effect. The water absorbed by epoxy-based composites causes reversible plasticization of the matrix and lowers its glass transition temperature [14]. Indeed, humidity and temperature cause dimensional changes and induce stresses in the laminate that degrade the fiber–matrix interface [15].

Figure 11: Shear stress × times curve profiles for non-aged (a) and aged (b) specimens.

It is well known that epoxy resins can suffer substantial reduction in T_g and mechanical properties when under the influence of water and especially at higher temperature [10], and continued hygrothermal ageing may lead to irreversible damage of the resin due to the susceptibility of the polymer to hydrolysis, oxidation, and changes in molecular weight [16]. The shear stress × strain (obtained with strain gage) curves are presented in Figure 12. For both non-conditioned (Figure 12a) and conditioned (Figure 12b) specimens the curve profiles were very linear, with $R^2 > 0.99$ for all specimens. Shear modulus also reduced after ageing, from $G_{12} = 5.44 \pm 0.48$ to $G_{12} = 3.89 \pm 0.19$.

Figure 12: Shear stress × strain curves for non-aged (a) and aged (b) specimens for the determination of shear modulus.

The failure mode of all specimens (Figure 13) was very similar, being characterized as horizontal cracking between the notches (HGN) and multi-mode cracking at the gage section between the notches (MGN). Crack started horizontally close to the top notch, probably due to some stress concentration caused by machining of the notches. Later, many delamination cracks perpendicular to the loading direction appeared at the midsection of the specimen.

Figure 13: Photographs of tested V-notched shear specimens.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the effect of weathering on tensile, shear and viscoelastic properties of flat carbon fiber/epoxy composites manufactured by filament winding were evaluated. The composite coupons were subjected to an accelerated hygrothermal conditioning for 60 days under 80 °C and relative humidity of 90%. Moisture absorption achieved a maximum of 0.42% in weight, with saturation at around 33 days. Non-Fickian kinetics was found to govern moisture absorption in the final stages of weathering probably due to the leaching of low-molecular weight molecules Matrix plasticization and a strong influence on T_g with ageing were also noticed, where the conditioned 90° specimen showed the smallest T_g .

Regarding mechanical properties, both tensile strength and modulus were found to decrease for aged laminates. In addition, the 90° specimens were more strongly affected by ageing, since a more matrix-dominated failure is expected in this direction. Shear properties were successfully evaluated through V-notched rail test and average shear modulus and strength reduced in as much as 30% and 40%, respectively.

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REFERENCES

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- [1] S. Pillay, U.K. Vaidya, G.M. Janowski, Effects of moisture and UV exposure on liquid molded carbon fabric reinforced nylon 6 composite laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*, **69**, 2009, pp. 839-846 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.03.021).
- [2] L.R. Bao, A.F. Yee, Moisture diffusion and hygrothermal aging in bismaleimide matrix carbon fiber composites: Part II-Woven and hybrid composites. *Composites Science and Technology*, **62(16)**, 2002, pp. 2111-2119 (doi: 10.1016/S0266-3538(02)00162-8).
- [3] O. Ishai, Environmental effects on deformation, strength, and degradation of unidirectional glass-fiber reinforced plastics. I. Survey, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, **15(7)**, 1973, pp. 486-490 (doi: 10.1002/pen.760150703).
- [4] Q. Zheng, R.J. Morgan, Synergistic thermal-moisture damage mechanisms of epoxies and their carbon fiber composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **27(15)**, 1993, pp. 1465-1478 (doi: 10.1177/002199839302701503).
- [5] L-R. Bao, A.F. Yee, Effect of temperature on moisture absorption in a bismaleimide resin and its carbon fiber composites, *Polymer*, **43(14)**, 2002, pp. 3987-3997 (doi: 10.1016/S0032-3861(02)00189-1).
- [6] B.G. Kumar, R.P. Singh, T. Nakamura, Degradation of carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy composites by ultraviolet radiation and condensation, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **36(24)**, 2002, pp. 2713-2733 (doi: 10.1177/002199802761675511).
- [7] D.E. Mouzakis, H. Zoga, C. Galiotis, Accelerated environmental ageing study of polyester/glass fiber reinforced composites (GFRPCs). *Composites Part B*, **39(3)**, 2008, pp. 467-475 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2006.10.004).
- [8] N.L. Batista, M.C.M. Faria, K. Iha, P.C. Oliveira, E.C. Botelho, Influence of water immersion and ultraviolet weathering on mechanical and viscoelastic properties of polyphenylene sulfide-carbon fiber composites, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composites*, **28(3)**, 2015, pp. 340-356 (doi: 10.1177/0892705713484747).
- [9] E.C. Botelho, J.C. Bravim Jr, M.K. Costa, M.C.M. Faria, Environmental effects on thermal properties of PEI/glass fiber composite materials, *Journal of Aerospace and Technology Management*, **5(2)**, 2013, pp. 241-254 (doi: 10.5028/jatm.v5i2.193).
- [10] E.C. Botelho, L.C. Pardini, M.C. Rezende, Hygrothermal effects on the shear properties of carbon fiber/epoxy composites, *Journal of Materials Science*, **41(21)**, 2006, pp. 7111-7118 (doi: 10.1007/s10853-006-0933-7).
- [11] V.M. Karbhari and G. Xian, Hygrothermal effects on high V_F pultruded unidirectional carbon/epoxy composites: moisture uptake, *Composites Part B*, **40(1)**, 2009, pp. 41-49 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2008.07.003).
- [12] R. Chandra, S.P. Singh, K. Gupta, Damping studies in fibre-reinforced composites - a review. *Composite Structures*, **46(1)**, 1999, pp. 41-51 (doi: 10.1016/S0263-8223(99)00041-0).
- [13] J.H.S. Almeida Jr., C. Staudigel, G.L.P. Caetano, S.C. Amico, Engineering properties of carbon/epoxy filament wound unidirectional composites, *Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Composite Materials – ECCM16 (Ed. Federico Paris), Seville, Spain, June 22-26, 2014*, pp. 1-8.
- [14] L.C. Bank and T.R. Gentry, Accelerated test methods to determine the long-term behavior of FRP composite structures: environmental effects, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **14(6)**, 1995, pp. 559-587 (doi: 10.1177/073168449501400602).
- [15] M.L. Costa, M.C. Rezende, S.F.M. Almeida, Strength of hygrothermally conditioned polymer composites with voids, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **39(21)**, 2005, pp. 1943-1961 (doi: 10.1177/0021998305051807).
- [16] G. Sala, Composite degradation due to fluid absorption, *Composites Part B*, **31(5)**, 2000, pp. 357-373 (doi: S1359-8368(00)00025-1).